

Beyond the Gray Arena Walls, How Façade Color Shapes the Spectators' Preference?

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Abstract

In recent years, the aesthetic design of sports stadiums, particularly their façade color, has drawn increasing research attention due to its impact on public perception, emotional response, and behavioral intention. This study investigates how the exterior color tone of a stadium (warm, cool, or neutral) affects viewers' aesthetic judgments and preferences. Using AI-generated images of fictional stadiums, participants evaluated each stadium's facade in terms of preference, beauty, simplicity, and familiarity on a 7-point Likert scale. As a result, paired sample t-tests revealed that cool-toned (blue) stadiums were significantly more preferred than both warm-toned (red) and neutral (gray) stadiums. Red stadiums were perceived as simpler and marginally more familiar, while gray stadiums were evaluated as significantly more beautiful than blue ones. By leveraging generative AI and online data collection, this study provides a novel, controlled method for isolating the perceptual effects of stadium facade color. These findings suggest that stadium color can significantly influence viewer perception and preference.

Keywords

Architecture, Façade Color, Public Perception, Behavioral Intention

Introduction

In modern society, sports have come to represent much more than just recreational activity. Having evolved throughout human history, sports are now recognized as an essential element of a healthy society. In particular, culturally shared sports strengthen the identity and unity of

communities. Most modern countries, including global sporting events like the Olympics, have established distinctive teams and stadiums in each city or region. These venues provide not only local residents but also visitors and international tourists with meaningful and memorable experiences. For example, in the United States, In 2023, the sports tourism market was valued at \$544.38 billion. The market is projected to grow from \$618.69 billion in 2024 to \$2,089.58 billion by 2032, reflecting a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 16.43% over the forecast period. This highlights the growing value of sports as a cultural, economic, and national asset beyond entertainment.

Among the many components of sports, the stadium plays a critical role as the physical space where sports unfold. It not only presents the physical space of player and spectator interaction, but its structural physicality offers immense architectural and aesthetic value. where players and spectators interact, but also a structure with significant architectural and aesthetic value. Given the scale of stadiums compared to ordinary buildings, the visual impact of a single stadium is undeniable.. Thus, the architectural aesthetics of a stadium can have a substantial influence on the identity(?) of its surrounding region. Stadiums often become city landmarks and continue to serve as tourist attractions even when no games are being held. In this sense, a stadium is far more than just a place to host sports. That is, it also serves as meaningful architectural symbol.

Recently, the appearance and façade of stadiums have become a subject of growing research interest (Akalin et al., 2010; Hou et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2024). In particular, studies have shown that the color of a building's exterior can strongly influence public perception. For example, Wang et al. (2024) examined how the color of aging residential buildings affects visual comfort using both eye-tracking data and subjective evaluations. They analyzed how hue, brightness, and saturation influenced visual fatigue and color preference by testing 56 color conditions on actual building exteriors. Using Tobii eye-tracking data from 50 undergraduate students, they measured gaze distance, pupil size, fixation duration, and number of fixations, while also collecting verbal ratings of comfort and preference. The results showed that highly saturated colors increased cognitive load and decreased preference, while brightness levels in the midrange (40–80%) were rated most comfortable. Moreover,

warm colors such as red, orange, and yellow, and certain cool colors like cyan and violet were rated more positively. Although the study focused on residential buildings, it suggests that both warm and cool color schemes can differentially impact the viewer's perception of building exteriors.

Other studies have explored how color in sports stadiums affects perception using real-world imagery. For example, Hou et al. (2024) explored the impact of stadium color design on spectator satisfaction. Drawing from actual images of stadiums in four Chinese cities, the study surveyed 554 participants in their 20s and 30s—including stadium managers, athletes, and fans. The study found that dynamic color schemes enhanced athletes' perceived emotional value, which, in turn, positively influenced spectator satisfaction. These results indicate that color in stadium architecture serves not only a functional purpose but also plays a significant emotional and psychological role. Additionally, the study highlighted the importance of color in reinforcing a stadium's brand identity and fostering fan loyalty and repeat attendance. However, because the sample consisted exclusively of athletes and fans, and the stimuli featured well-known stadiums, participants' prior familiarity and memories may have biased their responses. Future research should therefore incorporate more diverse, general audiences and utilize controlled stimuli to support broader generalizability.

In addition to image-based research, recent studies have quantified how people perceive architectural features. For instance, Arslan et al. (2023) examined the visual impact of 16 football stadiums built in Turkey between 2011 and 2021. They classified the stadiums based on whether the roof and facade were separated, their shape (circular or rectangular), and their color tone (neutral, warm+neutral, or cool+neutral). A total of 113 architecture majors and non-majors evaluated three facade images per stadium on five criteria—beauty, complexity, impressiveness, familiarity, and environmental harmony—using a 7-point semantic differential scale. The results indicated that stadiums featuring separate roofs and facades, circular forms, and neutral color palettes received more favorable evaluations. Notably, female participants rated the structures slightly lower in impressiveness, while architecture majors found them simpler and more familiar. This study underscores how facade design shapes both public perception and the urban visual landscape, providing valuable insights for

the planning of future public architecture.

Building on this existing research, the present study aims to examine how the color of a stadium facade influences aesthetic evaluations and psychological preferences using carefully controlled visual stimuli. Specifically, I propose the following hypothesis: Aesthetic judgments and preferences regarding stadium facades will differ depending on their color: The study compares warm-toned (e.g., red) and cool-toned (e.g., blue) stadium exteriors to assess differences in aesthetic appeal, satisfaction, and willingness to visit.

Methods

Participants

A total of 73 participants were randomly recruited through an online survey platform (e.g., SurveyMonkey). To ensure a balanced age distribution, participants were selected from a randomized pool spanning a range of age groups (see Figure 1). Of the respondents, 61% identified as female, 38% as male, and 1% chose not to disclose their gender. Upon completion of the survey, participants received incentives provided by the hosting platform.

Figure 1. Age Groups of Participants

Stimuli

This study employed images of fictional stadiums rather than real-world venues to control for architectural variables beyond color and to reduce the potential influence of participants' prior knowledge or personal experiences. To create these stimuli, I used an image-generation AI tool to produce stadium renderings. Initially, I generated general stadium images representing commonly recognized sports—soccer, basketball, baseball, American football, and hockey—based on their general popularity and familiarity. To increase architectural consistency across stadium types and to allow for sufficient variation in design features, I ultimately selected soccer, baseball, and American football stadiums based on the criterion that all three could plausibly be represented as dome-shaped venues. The AI tool used for image generation was the latest version of ChatGPT-4o as of 2025. The following prompts were used to create the stadium images.

(a) Example prompt for 'blue American football stadium'

*A realistic photographic depiction of the exterior of an **American football** stadium, highlighting large banners and team logos prominently displayed in bold shades of **blue**, electric **cyan**, and **navy**. The stadium facade features modern architecture with cool blue and metallic accents. Captured from an elevated perspective at twilight, the stadium's entrance and surrounding plaza are brightly illuminated with striking blue LED lighting effects, creating a vibrant, energetic atmosphere. The evening sky has a soft blend of dark **purples and deep blues**. Created Using: high-resolution photography, natural lighting, realistic textures, sports-themed detailing, sharp focus, dramatic lighting, cinematic aesthetics, balanced composition, hd quality, natural look --ar 16:9*

(b) Example prompt for red baseball stadium'

*A realistic photographic depiction of the exterior of a **Baseball** stadium, showcasing large banners and team logos prominently displayed in bold shades of **red**, including **fiery scarlet, deep crimson, and neon accents**. The stadium facade features sleek modern architecture with warm red tones and metallic highlights. Captured from an*

elevated perspective at twilight, the stadium entrance and surrounding plaza are illuminated by vivid red LED lighting, creating an energetic and vibrant atmosphere. The sky has soft blends of dark purples and deep red, accentuating the dynamic red glow. Created Using: high-resolution photography, realistic textures, natural lighting, sharp focus, sports-themed elements, dramatic lighting effects, cinematic aesthetics, balanced composition, hd quality, natural look --ar 16:9

As shown in the underlined portions of examples (a) and (b), only the type of sport (American football, baseball, or soccer) and the color tone (red, blue, or gray) were manipulated in the prompts, while all other instructions remained consistent. As a result, the stimuli shown in Figure 2 were generated.

Figure 2. AI-Generated Images of Stadiums

Measures

The study utilized several measures to assess stadium perception, stadium satisfaction, and willingness to visit stadium using a 5-point Likert scale to capture the degree of perception from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). To evaluate aesthetic judgments of stadium facades, this study employed a five-dimension aesthetic evaluation scale previously used for the same purpose by Arslan et al. (2023). The scale consisted of the following bipolar dimensions: Beautiful / Ugly, Simple / Complex, Impressive / Unimpressive, Familiar /

Unfamiliar, and Proportional / Non-Proportional. In addition, to measure participants' preferences for each stadium, this study adopted items from a preference scale used in prior research with a similar aim (Hou et al., 2024). This scale assessed participants' willingness to attend events held at the stadium and their satisfaction with the stadium's appearance. The full list of scale items is provided in the appendix.

Result and Discussion

Data Trimming

To ensure data quality, 21 participants were excluded for failing to complete all survey questions. An additional 7 responses were removed due to response patterns in which a single option on the 5-point Likert scale was selected more than 75% of the time, which was an indicator of extreme or inattentive responding that did not align with the intent of the survey. After this data cleaning process, 45 valid responses remained for further analysis.

Paired Sample t-test

	N	Mean	SD	SE	Coefficient of variation
gray_pref	45	3.481	0.858	0.128	0.247
red_pref	45	3.415	0.901	0.134	0.264
blue_pref	45	3.619	0.801	0.119	0.221
red_simple	45	4.141	1.300	0.194	0.314
gray_simple	45	3.793	1.040	0.155	0.274
red_familiar	45	4.185	1.410	0.210	0.337
blue_familiar	45	3.911	1.221	0.182	0.312
gray_beauty	45	3.704	1.168	0.174	0.315
blue_beauty	45	3.356	1.313	0.196	0.391

To examine how different stadium façade colors affect viewer perception, a series of paired sample t-tests were conducted on measures of preference, simplicity, familiarity, and beauty across warm tone (e.g., red), cool tone (e.g., blue), and neutral tone (e.g., gray) conditions.

Importantly, participants showed a significantly higher preference for blue facades compared to red facades, $t(44) = 2.554$, $p = .014$, and gray façades, $t(44) = 2.463$, $p = .018$, whereas no significant difference was found between gray and red façades, $t(44) = 0.709$, $p = .482$. This suggests that cool-toned stadium exteriors are generally more favored by respondents than either warm or neutral tones, while warm and neutral tones are perceived similarly in terms of preference.

Figure 3. Result of t-test for Preference to Red and Blue Façade Stadium

In terms of perceived simplicity, red facades were rated as simpler than gray facades, with results approaching statistical significance, $t(44) = 2.001$, $p = .052$. This near-significant difference may imply that warm colors like red contribute to a cleaner or more minimal impression compared to neutral gray tones. For familiarity, red façades were rated marginally more familiar than blue façades, $t(44) = 1.876$, $p = .067$, suggesting that participants may associate warm-colored stadiums with more common architectural experiences, although this effect did not reach full statistical significance.

Figure 4. Result of t-test for Familiarity to Red and Blue Façade Stadium

Lastly, participants evaluated gray façades as significantly more beautiful than blue façades, $t(44) = 2.182, p = .035$. This finding indicates that neutral tones may carry a refined, aesthetically pleasing quality that enhances the perceived beauty of the stadium. Taken together, these results demonstrate that stadium façade color meaningfully influences viewers' aesthetic and psychological responses, with cool tones being more preferred, warm tones perceived as simpler and more familiar, and neutral tones contributing positively to beauty evaluations.

Conclusion

This study examined how the color tone of stadium façades affects viewers' aesthetic perceptions and preferences, consistent with existing literature showing the importance of color on viewers' (i.e., consumers) perception in the field of sensory marketing, color psychology, and sport psychology (Elliot & Maier, 2014; Jin et al., 2019; Labrecque & Milne, 2012, Lindstrom, 2006). The findings revealed that cool-toned (blue) stadiums were rated significantly higher in overall preference, while neutral-toned (gray) stadiums were perceived as more beautiful. In contrast, warm-toned (red) stadiums were perceived as simpler and

marginally more familiar.

These findings are partly consistent with prior research. For example, Hou et al. (2024) emphasized the emotional value and satisfaction gained from innovative color designs in real stadiums, particularly when viewed by fans and athletes. While that study found emotional and brand-related benefits tied to vivid or unconventional colors, our results suggest that even in a controlled and fictional context, blue hues are broadly preferred by general viewers. Similarly, Arslan et al. (2023) found that neutral-toned stadiums received more positive evaluations across several dimensions of architectural perception. Our findings support this trend in the context of beauty ratings, reinforcing the aesthetic appeal of neutral tones.

A notable strength of this study lies in its methodological approach. By employing AI-generated stadium images and conducting an online survey, the study effectively controlled for confounding factors such as prior familiarity, architectural complexity, and real-world brand associations. Previous studies have shown that the use of emerging technologies can isolate specific design variables with greater precision, enabling novel avenues for architectural and perceptual research through tools such as eye-tracking (Wang et al., 2024) and virtual reality (Yildirim et al., 2019).

However, the study has limitations. Most notably, the sample size ($N = 45$ after data trimming) was relatively small, which may reduce the statistical power and generalizability of the findings. Future research should include larger, more demographically diverse samples and consider extending the stimuli set to explore more nuanced color variations and architectural features. Despite these limitations, the present findings contribute to the growing literature on environmental aesthetics and stadium design, highlighting how facade color alone can shape viewers' psychological and emotional responses.

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